

ENDURING RESILIENCE: THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF CRIMINOLOGY FACULTY AMIDST THE PANDEMIC

¹Yan-Yan K. Baladec, ²German B. Guaza, PhD, RCrim, ³Geraldine D. Rodriguez, EdD, PhD

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges

Graduate School

General Santos City, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8228550>

Published Date: 09-August-2023

Abstract: This phenomenological study aimed to understand the stories told by the Criminology Faculty of Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges, General Santos City on their teaching experiences amidst COVID-19 pandemic. This study utilized a qualitative research design which specifically used a phenomenological approach with the seven full-time Criminology Faculty chosen through purposive sampling. It was notably that the participants experienced were emerged into themes: participants were really challenged, adjustment is necessary, become tech savvy, flexibility is crucial, extend understanding towards students, practice time management, handle more responsibilities, appreciate job, and provide consultation. As to the challenges the following are the themes created: internet connection, health issue, gadget exposure, technology struggle, and frustration. For the coping mechanisms, the following are the themes: adjustment of technology, be optimistic, attend training and seminars, trust in the Lord, and learn from colleagues. And for the insights shared by the participants the following themes were created: accept changes, be grateful, develop oneself, adapt different teachings style, motivate students, and keep the willingness to learn. This study implicates to have a better contingency plan in case a new phenomenon happens and to focus for future researchers on the experiences of Criminology Faculty on the blended mode of education as well as to the adjustments returning of face-to-face classes.

Keywords: Criminology, faculty, pandemic, online class, phenomenology, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

“Do not live the same day repeatedly and call that a life. Menta, spiritual, and emotional evolution is all about” Kent (2021). Everything changes as time passes, and we must be dynamic and cope. Trying new things and learning from them for a person to grow up and excel in his work. The traditional approaches to education have been disrupted by the COVID-19 pandemic, creating a stressful and demanding environment for teachers. The mid-career teachers have particularly struggled to balance their work responsibilities with their home lives, and schools with more supportive working conditions have been more successful at helping them maintain a sense of success.

Correspondingly, research on remote emergency education during the COVID-19 pandemic has focused on nonresponse, campus social isolation strategies, and speedy responses to completely online courses. In Georgia, researchers Basilaia and Kvavadze investigated a case and found inadequate educational resources. Future trends in education include self-help, interactive online learning, innovations for unintentional instructional change, the revolution of learning management systems, and the development of collegial competence. (Crawford et al., 2020; Putra et al., 2020).

Additionally, COVID-19 was a significant health emergency that has caused over three-hundred and twenty-five thousand new cases of infection and six thousand fatalities in the Philippines. To fulfill the needs of students, higher education

institutions (HEIs) updated online learning models to include synchronous, real-time lectures and time-based outcomes evaluations. Making Higher Education Institutions free to create their policies without laws and regulations.

Furthermore, colleges and universities in Region-12 (SOCCSKSARGEN) have adapted to the flexible learning method due to the coronavirus pandemic. Thirteen HEIs received permission from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in Region Twelve to offer a limited number of in-person courses for the upcoming academic year, 2021–2022. To guarantee a smooth implementation, the involved schools work together actively (Gubalani, 2021).

Online classes were challenging during the COVID-19 pandemic due to a bad internet connection resulting in interruptions or forced class cancellations. Given that the majority of students have slow internet access and that the teacher extends the time allotted for the activity so that the student may submit it, a time-limited online assignment stresses the students. Students perceive online courses differently than traditional courses, and a key determinant in this perception is the course design. Technology-related problems were a significant impediment, and a forced transition to online learning may affect perceptions.

The issues with teachers' transitions from traditional to online classes demonstrate the need for this study immediately since no phenomenon should be allowed to put an end to education. Since this issue frequently arises even in face-to-face sessions, a simple teaching strategy is required, and it is only feasible having competent teachers. Teachers' mental health as they make the transition from conventional to online classrooms is a gap in this research. Everyone will gain from addressing this issue, including students, the administration of the school, and most importantly, the teachers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The COVID-19 pandemic has tested norms and conventions in various contexts; the novel nature of the disease, as well as the limited availability of approved therapeutics in some countries to combat the pandemic, has made non-clinical social distancing and hygiene measures the most viable options for combating the pandemic. The policies impact practically every element of human existence, including education, and to minimize the illness' transmission through social interaction, schools, universities, libraries, and other educational institutions were closed following disease management guidelines (Lau et al., 2020; Sahu, 2020; Van Lancker & Parolin, 2020).

Teaching Experiences Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic

The higher education system was put in shock by the COVID-19 pandemic on a global scale, with city-wide, regional, and country-wide lockdown orders put into place across the world. In most nations, decisions to cancel, postpone, or shift in-person lessons online took place within days. Other options included staying in, physical distance orders banning bigger gatherings and staying home. The arrival of online education in times of disruption is a common strategy, but prior events described regional responses (Ayebe-Arthur, 2017; Johnson et al., 2020; Swartz et al., 2018).

Furthermore, due to the expectation that they would be present and accessible for office hours at lunch and student group arrivals and departures throughout the day, several instructors reported having more work than they had before the school facilities were closed. Instructors also attempted to teach their children at home while doing all of this. Additionally, they spoke about locating the students they stopped hearing from (Jones & Kessler, 2020; Sawchuck & Samuels, 2020; Strauss, 2020).

Moreover, because of the implementation of remote education, teachers face difficulties due to a lack of guidance, training, and resources. According to Europeans, disadvantaged schools lack the digital capacity and infrastructure to provide distance learning. Private schools are familiar with the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), which is why they are more efficient than public schools. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted several deficiencies and injustices in educational institutions, ranging from a lack of accessibility to the computers and instructional materials required for online learning to a mismatch between resources and needs. (Milasi et al., 2020; Schleicher, 2020; Vulpe & Pribac, 2021).

Due to COVID-19, emergency e-learning is an expedited transition to online education. Prior to the pandemic, people in India were quietly unused to virtual teaching, but it is now the only medium or source used to fill the knowledge void. Amidst the pandemic, online teaching has both advantages and disadvantages for teachers and students, with obstacles such as a lack of online teaching experience, doubts about the effectiveness of online assessment and evolution, a lack of technical infrastructure, a lack of interaction, and an insufficient and expensive Internet connection. At the same time, it increased time and space flexibility, easy and rapid sharing of study material, quick feedback, more freedom to connect with faculty,

transportation and financial cost savings, improvements in teachers' and students' technological skills, and increased convenience and comfort (Bao, 2020; Henderson et al., 2020; Kamal & Illiyan, 2021).

In addition, the COVID-19 outbreak has caused fear and anxiety among several categories of professionals, including students, tourism and construction workers, healthcare professionals, and teachers. Teachers perceive Traditional face-to-face education as a teaching environment as largely unsafe, increasing their anxiety and fear. Moreover, the scarcity of resources such as teaching and learning materials and equipment, personal protective equipment (PPEs), facilities, and other logistics have led to heightened fear and anxiety of teachers regarding their safety in the school setting (Agormedah et al., 2020; Hagan et al., 2022; Quansah et al., 2022; Weinert et al., 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic is associated with unpredictability and low controllability for everyone, especially for teachers. Teachers in England and Argentina reported uncertainty about the future as a central theme. Teachers in Germany have also reported uncertainty, and demands and resources for coping with everyday professional life are changing. It is possible that teachers' emotional exhaustion increases during the pandemic (Bleck & Lipowsky, 2022; Kim & Asbury, 2020; Kim et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has raised teachers' perceived workload in many parts of the world. According to Canadian findings, teachers are experiencing increased stress and emotional tiredness during the pandemic. The teachers in the United States, Spain, and Finland also noted stress, burnout, and unpleasant emotions. Following the first lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic, a survey of German instructors discovered a reduced workload and tiredness. The pandemic has had minimal impact on Filipino teachers' mental health, with one-third reporting modest levels of perceived stress. According to Israeli studies, teacher stress levels have increased since the pandemic. Although more than half of survey respondents characterized online education as challenging, United Kingdom instructors also reported extremely high levels of well-being (Bleck & Lipowsky, 2022; Giovannella et al., 2020; Pöysä et al., 2021).

Moreover, noting the inadequate expertise of teachers in the current scenario must ensure the students get the most out of the pandemic modules. Regardless of the condition, instructors must employ accessible and suitable methodology to present their teachings successfully. Despite the problems provided by the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers continue to help by creating modules that serve as learning aids for pupils (Agayon et al., 2022; Lapada et al., 2020; Pentang, 2021).

In addition, teachers also discuss their concerns with modular distance learning, such as the expense of replication and being obliged to stay till eleven p.m. to finish the printing promptly. The Teachers Dignity Coalition claims that modular distance learning has increased teachers' workload, health hazards, and expenditures, causing them to beg for donations of bond paper and ink to print modules, demonstrating that using printed self-learning courses can be difficult. Teachers adapt to the new normal and perform their jobs despite problems that may obstruct their work (Agayon et al., 2022; Macaraeg et al., 2021; Malipot, 2020).

In that event, people who perform "human work" or something similar are susceptible to burnout, an illness characterized by intense exhaustion, depersonalization, and impaired individual success, which was a response to the constant, intense stress of overseeing others, especially while grieving or experiencing problems. Teachers must also design this new understanding so that students typically concerned with GPAs continue to receive direct feedback on their understanding, that the most pleasant students have opportunities to share their ideas and engage in meaningful conversation, and that they make the best use of available technology. School innovators can reduce teachers' stress by creating favorable working conditions and fostering effective teacher-student relationships, and to make it; schools should use procedures that encourage good understudy behavior and take care of themselves to effectively interact with others. As a result, it will help teachers to better think about others and perform at their best (Hart, 2020; Ketchell, 2018; Robosa et al., 2021).

Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic is associated with unpredictability and low controllability for everyone, especially teachers. Interviewing the teachers in England and Argentina reported uncertainty about the future as a central theme. The teachers in Germany have also reported uncertainty, and demands and resources for coping with everyday professional life are changing, which possibly increases teachers' emotional exhaustion during the pandemic (Bleck & Lipowsky, 2022; Kim & Asbury, 2020; Klusmann et al., 2020).

Furthermore, teachers worry sensitively and endure stress while utilizing technology, demonstrating that when the new learning paradigm shifts to online forms. Several teachers are not "Millennials" or "Gen Z" who are likelier to be sad since they are uninformed or unprepared to teach remotely, leading to dissatisfaction and frustration among educators. One of the primary causes of secondary education instructors in public schools experiencing stress is their commitment to and concern

for their students. Several educators believe they have a moral responsibility to their pupils' well-being. (Al-Fudail & Mellar, 2008; Alvarina et al. 2022; Dziuban et al. 2018; Nyambongi, 2014).

Moreover, teachers have faced a lot of constraints and challenges due to the COVID-19 outbreak, but they have continued to produce modules that serve as learning aids for students. The teachers are concerned about the high cost of reproduction and must stay at school until evening to complete the printing on time. The modular distance learning model has resulted in more work, increased health hazards, and increased expenses, prompting teachers to request bond paper and ink contributions to print modules. Teachers must learn to deal with the new normal and carry out their responsibilities in the face of impediments (Caratiquit & Caratiquit, 2022; De Villa & Manalo, 2020; Lapada et al., 2020; Macaraeg et al., 2021).

A study conducted on the experiences and challenges faced by educators during the pandemic turned out that teachers are facing an insufficiency of resources for online teachings, such as a reliable internet connection and online platform, as well as inadequate skills to handle students online, resulting in several teachers and schools were caught off guard and shifted to online teaching. Transitioning to online teaching, most instructors, according to a report, are somewhat or highly uncertain, stressed, anxious, overwhelmed, sad, and lonely. Teachers managed these problems and maintained a positive view of teaching and learning despite them. (Edara et al. 2021; Robosa et al. 2021; Schaffhauser, 2020).

Furthermore, in China, the research found that the pandemic had a major impact on instructors' and students' well-being, with 35.1% reporting moderate anxiety symptoms and 21% reporting sadness. Meanwhile, German teachers experienced a medium-to-high amount of stress during the lockdown. In contrast, in the UK, teachers reported high levels of anxiety, and in Chile, the pandemic negatively affected teachers' quality of life (Allen et al., 2020; Hidalgo-Andrade et al., 2021; Huang & Zhao, 2020; Klapproth et al., 2020).

Coping Mechanisms Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic

Since the pandemic appears to be lingering, teachers must devise coping mechanisms for the physical and psychological reactions associated with the pandemic, such as anxiety and stress. Based on available research, teachers have made various adjustments in response to the pandemic, including shifting to digital and online learning and implementing psychological coping strategies. Moreover, Klapproth et al. (2020) discovered that although most German teachers faced COVID-19 adversities, they dealt with them functionally. In other words, coping strategies are behavioral and cognitive strategies individuals use to manage painful crises, conditions, and demands. This strategy divides into four categories: cognitive approach, cognitive avoidance, behavioral approach, and behavioral avoidance (Baker, 2021; Quansah et al., 2022; Roy et al., 2020).

Additionally, teachers' awareness and comprehension of COVID-19 infections/transmission, basic hygiene concepts, and prevention techniques are critical in adopting effective control measures that may help them feel less worried, stressed, and unhappy. Surely, teachers aware of COVID-19 symptoms, transmissions, and prevention measures are more likely to utilize adaptive or active coping methods to lessen psychological consequences or mental health illnesses such as worry, sorrow, fear, stress, and vice versa. In this case, the previous research on teachers' understanding of or familiarity with COVID-19 has resulted in conflicting results in various populations across jurisdictions. As an illustration, the general population in Europe and North America was generally well-informed about COVID-19, but some misunderstandings were noted. Parallel to this, it has been discovered that many Asian populations comprehend and are aware of COVID-19 to a moderate to high degree. (Fang et al., 2021; Geldsetzer, 2020; Hagan et al., 2022; Teo et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021).

Furthermore, studies suggest that, even though teachers' motivations for exploring were more personal than professional, they nevertheless saw a few benefits from engaging in the classroom and study-hall-based research for their professional development. Suppose school leaders can assist in minimizing teacher stress by creating working circumstances that allow educators to feel less pressure and commit to working more frequently. Moreover, the schools can also assist in reducing educator stress by promoting strong teacher-student interactions and implementing mechanisms that promote excellent student behavior. However, educators must also deal with themselves to deal with others. Notably, educators lose their ability to think about others when they cannot think about themselves properly (Hart, 2020; Ketchell, 2018; Robosa et al., 2021).

Additionally, technology has revolutionized how education is accessible and affected the roles of teachers and students. Furthermore, it facilitates the creation of instructional materials by teachers, offers new opportunities for collaboration and learning among students, and much more. Moreover, entering a new era of education could take place wherever and whenever to choose due to the internet's widespread accessibility and the abundance of mobile devices that can connect to

it. However, the new era's course will depend on individuals creating and delivering education and the new tools they can use to improve it. Since practical education will become more accessible if this opportunity is taken up, using technology to revolutionize our education (Ahmadi, 2018; Kawinkoonlasate, 2020; Online Purdue, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused significant increases in k12 education costs, and educators are devising materials to assist students in learning and staying healthy during school closures. Hence, teachers should be adaptable and communicate concerns, teach positively and focus on student support, maintain a course curriculum that is too complicated for students to learn online, on computers and the internet, and obtain appropriate permission to substitute a required topic. As a result, the teaching and learning environment might affect the way standardized textbooks are organized and how it presents the content, and employing a module offers a more flexible learning environment for teachers and students (Barry & Kanematsu, 2020; Cheng & Bakar, 2017; Dilna et al., 2022).

Hopes and Aspirations Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic

Two more personal characteristics that possibly affect a teacher's resilience are self-esteem and a sense of purpose. In this case, a study in Okinawa showed that teachers' self-esteem and resilience are connected and that perceived mattering is favorably correlated with resilience and negatively correlated with stress and burnout. To summarize, the significant elements contributing to teachers' resilience are self-esteem, dispositional hope, mattering, and crisis self-efficacy (Ainsworth & Oldfield, 2019; Baguri et al., 2022; Ratanasiripong et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the coronavirus pandemic has led to a need to rethink and redesign instructional strategies to respond to the rising demand for higher, continuing education. Hence, a pedagogical transition from traditional methods to the contemporary way of teaching and learning may be reflected in online education. Moreover, remote education could contribute to democratization and the evolution of the scholarship of teaching by improving the ability to recognize which material is essential to students' understanding and learning, organize and deliver course material, and seek solutions to use all the benefits of new technologies. Additionally, adaptability and innovation of teachers' behavior are central to a competitive society advancing technologically with astonishing speed. This time also provided excellent opportunities for developing teaching skills in other learning environments, such as online; the literature already in existence on the effects of COVID-19 on teaching has primarily concentrated only on the challenges faced by teachers when transitioning to online teaching (Ma et al., 2021; Mishra et al., 2020; Raducu & Stanculescu, 2021).

The related literature, studies, and articles that were cited and included in this research contribute by giving ideas such as utilizing coping mechanisms to reduce the effect of the phenomenon, knowledge of what researchers have found to be able to determine the underlying reasons for why the participants act and experiencing such things, and facts showing challenges the participants experienced that may come and disrupt what is already existing, but there is always a solution.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative research method, specifically the phenomenological research design. Thus, qualitative research is a type of social science research that seeks to draw meaning from non-numerical data to better understand social life through studying specific groups or regions (Crossman, 2020). Moreover, the study utilized phenomenological research design to provide systematic information about lived experiences of criminology faculty at Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges, General Santos City.

Role of the Researcher

The researcher must ensure integrity and respect for the participants by anticipating ethical difficulties at all phases of the research. Moreover, the researcher must follow ethical guidelines to achieve the study's objectives.

As an inquirer, the researcher had adequate coordination in acquiring access to the site and the participants. Furthermore, the researcher also got authorization from Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges' administration by submitting a letter of approval addressed to the college president thru the Dean of Criminal Justice Education.

As interviewer, the participants were asked permission and given a consent letter before being used as research informants, and during the interview, all participants received a copy of the consent. Consequently, the researcher ensured that interviews occurred with an interview guide detailing the outline covered. Furthermore, the purpose of the research is explained to the participants, and with their permission, the researcher records their replies, analyses, and interpretations. Moreover, the researcher assured the participants that their responses were entirely private and confidential in compliance with the Data Privacy Act. Additionally, the interview occurred at the most convenient location and time for the participants.

Meanwhile, a qualitative research technique known as an interview focuses on collecting data via the use of questions, and interviews are conducted by two or more people, one of whom is the interviewer who asks the questions. (George, 2022).

As an observer, the researcher excluded prejudice, bias, and personal preferences to ensure the study's accuracy; to achieve it, the researcher had to pay great attention to ethical issues when conducting the study and pay attention to the participants' shared experiences. However, the researcher emphasized that participation was voluntary and that participants may withdraw from the study at any time, and by giving the participants a pseudonym, the researcher was able to protect the participant's identity from prying eyes. In observation in a systematic and meaningful way, qualitative research is one of the oldest and most fundamental research methods used to collect data using one's senses (Smit & Onwuegbuzie, 2018).

As an advocate, the researcher's main goal is to address issues and provide a voice for others. Furthermore, the objective of this qualitative study was for the researcher to represent the participants in this study. Moreover, the researcher believes that this qualitative study is incomplete unless an effort is made to help the research participants or the communities in which they speak. Also, the study's advocacy goal was to enlighten readers about the preparation and actions they should take to respond to the problems and obstacles they faced during the COVID-19 epidemic. Finally, being an advocate is all about speaking for the research participants, and it is related to using QLR to "give a voice" to those with none (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

As a transcriber, honesty was crucial, and to win the participants' trust, the researcher must report the transcribed material appropriately. Furthermore, the researcher transcribed the data collected honestly to become more reliable and accurate. Hence, the researcher's responsibility was to translate the raw data obtained while the study was conducted. In addition, the initial phase in data analysis, close observation of the data through repeated attentive listening, was what transcription implies. Therefore, understanding the data and focusing on what was there rather than expectations might help create realizations or ideas that come to mind when conducting analysis, which is feasible by text-formatting the captured audio data (Bailey, 2008).

As an analyst, there is a need to guarantee that the information obtained from the data collection is correct and will help the study. Therefore, the researcher must ensure that it undergoes a thorough strategic analysis. Hence, the data analysis completes once the researcher has obtained the required information for the study. Furthermore, the researcher for this study will analyze qualitative data using Creswell's six stages. Moreover, after analysis, the data must be verified to guarantee the results' validity, generalizability, and reliability. (Creswell, 2013).

Research Participants

Purposive sampling was used to determine the participants of this study. Non-probability sampling was chosen based on demographic characteristics and the study's goal. In fact, Kelly (2010) utilized purposive sampling to select respondents who are most likely to provide relevant and useful information, and it was a method of discovering and choosing instances that will efficiently employ limited research resources.

The participants of this research were the seven (7) Criminology Faculty of Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges, General Santos City. In this case, participants were chosen since the study's main point is the teaching experiences amidst the pandemic. Hence, Full-time Criminology Faculty were the only ones in this research who experienced the pandemic. In detail, three (3) participants for in-depth interviews since they have different free time and are hard to group, and four (4) participants for focus group discussions since they have the same free time and are easy to group.

The Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges' criminology faculty members who worked there throughout the stipulated period were the subject of the inclusion criteria for this study on their continuing resilience in the face of the pandemic. Consequently, this research aimed to document the lived experiences of faculty members willing to share their experiences during this trying period and who had personally experienced the consequences of the pandemic in their professional and personal lives.

On the contrary, the exclusion criteria of this study involved individuals who were not employed as criminology faculty members at Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges during the specified period. Thus, individuals who had not directly experienced the impacts of the pandemic on their professional and personal lives were excluded from the study. During this special time, it was essential to focus on faculty members who could furnish valuable insight into their experiences and resilience.

Withdrawal criteria took shape to prioritize the well-being and voluntary engagement of research participants. Hence, if any participant expressed discomfort, distress, or a desire to withdraw from the study at any point, they have the option to do so without facing any negative consequences. Moreover, a participant's withdrawal did not impact their relationship with Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges or their employment status, ensuring their autonomy and safeguarding their rights as research participants.

Data Collection

The following paragraphs demonstrate how data collection happens after obtaining consent or authorization and carefully checking to ensure that the interview guide is acceptable. Thus, through observation, the following procedure occurs to gather the needed data for this study

First and foremost, a research questionnaire was created to be validated by the experts. Secondly, once the research questionnaire was validated, an application was created asking permission from the ERC and waiting for approval. Third, as the ERC approved the research questionnaire, the researcher prepared a letter addressed to the college president thru the Dean of the College of Criminal Justice to gather data. Fourth, an informed consent was created to be signed by the participants. Lastly, the researcher explained the urgency of the study and the importance of participants' voluntary participation. Moreover, data gathering happens once all the participants are informed and get their consent.

According to King and Horrocks (2010), developing relationships is vital to successful qualitative interviewing. Thus, through interaction that occurred during the interview, the data, as well as any pertinent extra information, was supplied. Nevertheless, qualitative interviews can be documented or videotaped, which aids in data transcription, coding, and analysis which is significantly beneficial. In contrast, there are drawbacks to qualitative interviews, such as the fact that conducting interviews takes time, especially if they are videotaped and thoroughly transcribed. Obviously, the researcher was required time to plan interviews, gather and record data, transcribe code, and evaluate the data (Bryman, 2012). In this case, scheduling adequate time is a common interview flaw that might influence respondents' responses.

The data was the lived experiences of the Criminology Faculty, especially on teaching and their experiences amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. In this case, the researcher shows the transcribed data for validation and accuracy according to the participant's responses. Nevertheless, it was included in the informed consent that participants may add or delete any transcribed data.

Analysis of Data

The methods for phenomenological data processing are identical for all psychological phenomenologists that describe the methodology (Moustakas, 1994; Polkinghorne, 1989). In other words, data analysts sift through the data, such as interview transcriptions, and identify important statements, words, or quotes that offer insight into how the participants perceived the phenomena based on the data from the first and second research questions. Furthermore, it was referred to as horizontalization by Moustakas (1994). Moreover, the researcher then turns these noteworthy sentences into themes by creating clusters of meaning.

Utilize a thematic analysis to determine the data collected. Hence, the experiences they shared in each stand-in question were grouped during the interview and categorized to create themes wherein the researcher recognized the primary themes and essential concepts in the participants' responses.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part merged the themes that described the teaching experiences of the Criminology Faculty during the COVID-19 pandemic. Three main themes emerged from the participants' responses: experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights.

Teaching Experiences of the Participants Amidst the Pandemic

As to the experiences of the Criminology Faculty, nine essential themes emerged. It challenged the participants, adjustment is necessary, becoming tech-savvy, flexibility is crucial, extending understanding towards students, practicing time management, handling more responsibilities, appreciating the job, and providing consultation.

Table 1. Experiences of Criminology Faculty on their teaching during COVID-19 pandemic

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Teachers faced many difficulties Curriculum became challenging Student's behavior changed Work became difficult Interacting with students was hard	Participants were really challenged
Adjusted with the new normal Strive hard to learn the use of technology Adjusted with the attitude of students Teachers need to do extra effort Teaching strategies were improved Practiced proper health protocol	Adjustment is Necessary
Teachers were able to practice the use of technology Technology was used to communicate with students New online platforms were introduced Exposed students to the use of technology Became computer literate Gadgets were used for educational purposes	Become Tech Savvy
Able to go extra miles for students Choose to work despite health issues Sacrifice time for the students Can work despite in the period of adjustment Able to still do school works even when at home	Flexibility is Crucial
Listen to the concerns of students Understand the student's situation Extend patience Provide Humanitarian Consideration	Extend Understanding Towards Students
Teachers manage their time well Can do works and reports Manage teaching time Make calendar of activities Handle Work Under Pressure Avoid Procrastination	Practice Time Management
Observed what the government rules Utilized different teaching platforms to teach students Gave extra effort at work Managed the online class well Adapted the use of technology Printed modules to continue education Made PowerPoint presentations for online classes	Handle More Responsibilities
Do the work well Value work Realize that work is the bread and butter Appreciate that work is the source of income Grab teaching opportunities	Appreciate the Job
Have a one-on-one conversation with students Reach-out with students Communication became more important Respond with their concern Being available all the time for students' queries	Provide Consultation

Challenged Participants. Since the arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic, many people lost their jobs, and some remain but experienced a significant change, and one profession that has experienced change is the teachers. Teachers experienced many difficulties. There are changes in the student's behavior, making it hard for teachers to interact and leading to work becoming challenging.

According to a study done by the University of Pennsylvania in 2016 by Wyman (2020), high-stress levels affect the instructors' efficacy and capacity to educate children correctly. It shows that teachers have poor anger control and procrastination due to mental and emotional distractions. In addition, according to a study-based analysis, instructors in the new regular need to use new professional and emotional management methods and forms to adjust to the viral pandemic changes completely. The paper outlined a timeframe for response management, including advice, technology use, and the formation of digital recreation activities.

Adjustment is Necessary. As hardships and difficulties have arrived amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, it is unfeasible to be effective and efficient at work without adjustment. The same statements said by the participants that they need to strive more in learning technology and make more extra effort than usual. In addition to that, participants must follow health protocols.

Teachers must ensure that students get the most out of the pandemic modules (De Villa & Manalo, 2020). According to Tosun et al. (2021), teachers are unskillful in dealing with the current scenario. Pentang (2021) remarked that regardless of the conditions, instructors must employ accessible and suitable methodology to present their teachings successfully. Despite the problems provided by the COVID-19 epidemic, teachers continue to help by creating modules that serve as learning aids for pupils (Lapada et al., 2020). However, Malipot (2020) emphasized that teachers also discuss their concerns with modular distance learning, such as the expense of replication and being obliged to stay till 11:00 p.m. to finish the printing promptly. According to Macaraeg et al. (2021), the country's Teachers Dignity Coalition claims that modular distance learning has increased teachers' workload, health hazards, and expenditures, causing them to ask for bond paper and ink donations to print modules. These demonstrate that using printed self-learning courses can be difficult. Teachers adapt to the new normal and perform their jobs despite problems that may obstruct their work.

Become Tech Savvy. Affiliated with the adjustments, particularly in technology, teachers become computer literate. According to them, since they use technology for education, introduced to new online platforms, technology was used in communicating with students are the reasons.

There are exceptions: many instructors welcome the arrival of technology as a way to transform the way they educate. Nascimbeni and Burgos (2016) substantiated that although OER and Creative Commons licensing is growing, many higher education institutions are experiencing finite sharing and reluctance to embrace OER. Rolfe discovered that a shortage of time and IT infrastructure were impediments to resource sharing among her participants in her research academics from a Health and Life Sciences Faculty.

Flexibility is Crucial. Since, as always, changes are constant wherein teachers should be flexible, capable of doing things efficiently, and can work despite the period of adjustments. Ineffective educators lead to incompetent students, which is why there should be sacrifice of time and go the extra mile for students.

According to research on online learning issues in the classroom Nyambongi (2014), teachers could be better in mixed forms of learning. Blended learning is not the preferred mode of education for instructors since they are not trained or equipped to teach remotely. This perplexity produces dissatisfaction and frustration among educators (Dziuban et al., 2018). Thus, stress causes and manifestations in secondary education instructors in public schools. This study showed that time and care for pupils are critical causes of teacher stress, and many educators believe they have a moral responsibility to their pupils' well-being.

Extend Understanding. The COVID-19 pandemic globally affects people. From children to teenagers up to adults. From elementary to high school up to college, as well as those employed or unemployed. It is time for people to be understanding since everyone experiences hardships. According to the participants, they view teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic as a period of understanding. They said teachers should listen to students' concerns, understand their situation, extend their patience, and provide humanitarian considerations.

Teachers must recognize that many pupils nowadays need to be more energized about studying printed material (Schrum & Levin, 2009). Students are more willing to read online content or listen to podcasts, and teachers must recognize it since today's learning differs from the past.

Practice Time Management. Most of the educators were already overloaded with workloads. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has come so that things could be inappropriately handled without time management. According to the participants, there should be a calendar of activities to manage the teaching time, can be handled work even under pressure, and can do reports. By avoiding procrastination, workloads could finish together with time management.

Teachers are separated from their understudies and colleagues worldwide (Hart, 2020). One documented cause of teacher burnout is the feeling of alienation and dejection that might arise from the existing situation. Burnout is "a disorder of passionate fatigue, depersonalization, and diminished individual achievement that can occur among people who do 'human work' or some variation thereof." It is a reaction to the constant, passionate strain of managing other people, particularly when they are grieved or having issues. Educators should not only learn new teaching platforms such as Zoom, Canvas, and Google Classroom, but they must also plan this new learning to ensure that understudies who are concerned about their GPAs continue to receive simple feedback on their understanding, that the most social understudies have opportunities to share their thoughts and participate in real and meaningful conversation as well as community work in a virtual space, and that they use best piecing techniques.

Handle More Responsibilities. as what aforementioned earlier, the arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic makes educators overloaded with workloads. In traditional learning, a lesson plan and a book prepare a lesson. In contrast, creating PowerPoint, enrolling students in the LMS, and observing the rules given by the authority since face-to-face or contact education is impossible are the additional preparation for teachers.

Teachers and students consider online communication etiquette in an online learning setting Quintos et al. (2020). Another challenge online learning faces is technical concerns among teachers, students, and their parents. Slow and unreliable internet connections may impede their ability to connect and participate in class. According to Sunil Kumar's paper, adaptability struggles, computer literacy, time management, and self-motivation are significant challenges for teachers and learners in e-learning.

Appreciate the Job. The COVID-19 pandemic affects not only the health of all people but also their occupations. Many people lost their jobs and endured many hardships amidst the pandemic. Some remain to have work but in a skeletal mode which is still not enough to provide basic needs. Participants view the COVID-19 pandemic as a blessing wherein they still have jobs. Despite the pandemic, they do work well, value their work, and instill in their mind that their work is their bread and butter and source of income. In conclusion, people should grab the opportunity amidst the pandemic once they still have a job.

Many challenges were reported by Setiawan (2020), affecting both instructors and students. According to UNESCO (2020), more than 70% of the world's student population has been impacted in various forms by the closure of educational institutions. Meanwhile, some nations saw regional closures, while others experienced national closures (ECW, 2020). This section examined pertinent articles to understand how the education sector works in different settings.

Provide Consultation. The effect of the COVID-19 pandemic was very destructive, in which the educational welfare of students may be broken or destroyed. Due to high technological demands and an internet connection, some need help to afford it and think of stopping their studies. According to participants, communication with the students is significant. Teachers can have one-on-one conversations, reach out to their students, respond to their concerns, and be available for students' queries.

Given the benefits and downsides of both modalities, it is critical to strike a balance between face-to-face delivery and delivery in online venues. According to Heinze and Procter (2003), the online environment has the disadvantage of having inadequate social contact expected in a traditional setting. Furthermore, according to Salmon (2002), this might lead to a loss of motivation in the less autonomous student, which they generally get from social engagement and relationships. Moreover, Rogers (2001) recommends that the institution consider the compromise or mix between the online and face-to-face components. Factors such as instructional objectives, student characteristics, the quality of online resources, and trainer expertise, according to Osguthorpe and Graham (2003), are crucial in achieving a balance between face-to-face and online techniques.

Table 2. The Challenges and Coping Mechanisms of the Criminology Faculty During COVID-19 Pandemic

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Challenges	
Difficulty in signal Classes were interrupted due to poor internet connectivity Not technology wise Internet connection got lost sometimes	Internet Connection
Affect psychological health Struggle with the virus cause by pandemic Became physically unhealthy Got sick due to prolonged use of computer Got sick due to working too much Experienced hypertension	Health Issue
Too much used of different gadgets Exposure to gadgets triggered the eyes Got headache because of using computer or cellphone Spend too much time in online classes	Gadget Exposure
Unfamiliar with different online platforms Unable to use technology very well Adjust with online teaching Find it difficult to prepare soft copy materials for students Struggle with the use of excel	Technology Struggle
Negativity happened Work Became Stressful Felt like quitting due to the pandemic Frustrated with the fact that they were unable to learn new trends Frustrated whenever signal got lost	Frustrations
Coping Mechanisms	
Handled the difficulties on online modalities Watched YouTube videos and other online tutorial on how to use different types of platform Exposed teachers to the use of online platforms Improve teachers' technological skills Utilized MyopenLMS to provide quality learning	Adjustment on Technology
Be sensitive to the guidance of the Lord Always pray to have a good health Pray for everyone's safety Pray to boost mental health Stay strong and have faith in God	Trust in the Lord
Be positive always Think that teachers can do many things Accept what happened during the pandemic Use gadget wisely Be prepared all the time Never think of quitting Be open-minded and embrace change	Be Optimistic
The institution provided training and seminars for teachers Boost self-confidence through seminars Join training about technology enhancement Join face-to-face training and seminar on the use of different online platforms Improve oneself	Attend Training and Seminars
Listen to the ideas of others Be willing to learn from co workers Ask on how to navigate the computer Colleagues were willing to offer help Colleagues also shared their knowledge about the use of technology	Learn from Colleagues

Challenges of the Participants Amidst the Pandemic

Five essential themes emerged in Table two for the challenges of participants, internet connection, health issues, too much exposure to gadgets, struggle with technology, and frustrations.

Internet Connection. One of the challenges encountered by the participants brought by the COVID-19 pandemic is the internet connection wherein they need to have the internet connection to teach or provide lectures. Mobile data connection from mobile phones is an alternative to it. However, it is not reliable because of its weakness. Sometimes, once the internet connection got lost, it interrupted the online lecture, and troubleshooting was challenging because not all educators are technology-wise.

It is well known that children and parents at public schools frequently report needing internet access at home or that parents cannot afford to purchase loads regularly Quintos et al. (2020). Most schools still need a clear plan for acquiring the necessary technology and resources to create usable online programs. Furthermore, instructors' digital literacy is critical for online learning. Teachers and students consider online communication etiquette in an online learning setting. Another challenge online learning faces is technical concerns among teachers, students, and their parents. Slow and unreliable internet connections may impede their ability to connect and participate in class. Both teachers and learners, adaptability struggles, computer literacy, time management, and self-motivation are significant challenges in e-learning.

Health Issues. Primarily, the concern amidst the COVID-19 pandemic is the health of everyone. Works, businesses, and studies cannot efficiently finish if there is a health risk. The pandemic affects psychological and physical health. According to the participants teaching amidst the pandemic got them sick due to working too much since more responsibility arrived and due to prolonged use of computers.

The country's Teachers Dignity Coalition claims that modular distance learning has increased teachers' workload, health hazards, and expenditures, causing them to beg for bond paper and ink donations to print modules (De Villa & Manalo, 2020). These demonstrate that using printed self-learning courses can be difficult. However, despite problems that may obstruct their work, teachers adapt to the new normal and perform their jobs.

Gadgets Exposure. According to the participants, as they used technology to conduct lectures, they may use different gadgets. As stated earlier that communication with students is significant. They must spend more time in online classes or platforms, which prolongs the use of gadgets resulting in triggered eyes and headaches.

Because of the potential adverse effects on health, using gadgets is a severe worry (Pachiyappan, et., al., 2021). Many health issues, including eye strain, finger discomfort, backache, neck pain, and sleep disruptions, have been linked to prolonged usage of electronics. Depending on how much people spend time (length and frequency) using devices, it has a negative physiological, psychological, social, and emotional impact. The danger of youngsters using technology excessively while stressed is also rising.

Technology Struggle. Not all teachers are technology-wise. According to participants, most of the time, they need to familiarize themselves with different online platforms. Making and preparing soft copies of materials was hard for them, especially in using the Excel applications on the computer.

Without sufficient professional development for teachers, no effort in schools will be successful, especially when it comes to the use of technology (Drayton et al., 2010). Teachers must have the opportunity to explore their beliefs, how to integrate technology and experimental tactics, and how to obtain insight into student work utilizing technology as part of their professional development.

Frustration. As a result of those struggles with technology, teachers are frustrated. According to the participants, sometimes negativity happens since some projects or activities are still pending within their time frame, and work becomes stressful. Other participants stated that sometimes they felt like quitting due to the challenges brought on by the pandemic. They were also frustrated that they were unable to learn new trends. As well as when the signal got lost.

One documented cause of teacher burnout is the feeling of alienation and dejection that might arise from the existing situation (Hart, 2020). Burnout is a disorder of intense fatigue, depersonalization, and diminished individual achievement that can occur among people who do 'human work' or some variation thereof." It is a reaction to the constant, passionate strain of managing other people, particularly when they are grieved or having issues. Educators should not only learn new teaching platforms such as Zoom, Canvas, and Google Classroom, but they must also plan this new learning to ensure that understudies who are concerned about their GPAs continue to receive simple feedback on their understanding, that the most social understudies have opportunities to share their thoughts and participate in real and meaningful conversation as well as community work in a virtual space, and that they use best piecing techniques.

Coping Mechanism of the Participants Amidst the Pandemic

Adjusting to the use of technology, trusting in the Lord, being optimistic, attending training and seminars, and learning from colleagues were the five themes that emerged as the coping mechanisms of the participants.

Adjust with the use of technology. The changes made by the participants, such as watching YouTube video tutorials on how to use different online platforms, utilizing MyOpenLMS to provide quality education, and exposing themselves to online platforms, improve their technical skills and ability to handle difficulties in online modalities.

According to McNaughton and Billot (2016), the "closed classroom door" is a tradition in teaching, and most lecturers have built their teaching materials. Even when technology, such as an LMS, is employed, most interactions with students occur in the classroom, and interaction and activities are hidden from the outside. Despite this, using technology in the classroom might alter the role of instructors, which they may regard as a loss of control. Anything that jeopardizes the conventional classroom interaction threatens the instructors' identity (Hanson, 2009). However, there are exceptions: many instructors welcome the arrival of technology as a way to transform the way they educate. Although the usage of OER and Creative Commons licensing is growing, many higher education institutions are experiencing no sharing and reluctance to embrace OER. Rolfe discovered that a shortage of time and IT infrastructure were impediments to resource sharing among her participants in her research academics from a Health and Life Sciences Faculty.

Trust in the Lord. According to the participants, we always remember where we came from to make and finish the job efficiently. Tributing all their works to the *Lord* by constantly praying for good health and mind. Always have faith in God and be sensitive to the guidance of the *Lord*.

Consistently maintaining your faith and avoiding separating excellent or bad times from your faith are two ways to rely on God through difficult times (Meidl, 2014). Find practices that bring you peace by often going to church. Lay the struggles before God and rely on support systems. Finally, always find good. Have a heart of gratitude and find some good every day, claim it well, and tell someone of that good.

Be optimistic. According to participants, be cheerful always. Sometimes jobs are very tiring since conflicts and workloads are always there, resulting to unable to finish jobs or projects. However, it is feasible by accepting what happened during the pandemic, using gadgets wisely, being always prepared, never thinking of quitting, being open-minded, and embracing changes.

Teachers continue to manage the new normal in education despite the COVID-19 pandemic danger, displaying their resiliency (Lagat, 2021). This descriptive correlational study assessed 150 instructors' optimism, work-related stress, and emotional tiredness. It also examined the link between these three factors. The weighted mean, standard deviation, and Pearson *r* were used to examine the data. The findings showed that instructors were resilient in the pandemic, with a high degree of optimism and a low level of occupational stress and emotional weariness caused by COVID-19. Additionally, this study has demonstrated that optimism is not connected to emotional weariness or job stress, although it identifies a strong association between these two factors.

Attend Training and Seminars. Another way for participants to cope with challenges is to join training and seminars, which will give knowledge about the new standard classes. According to them, joining training and seminars will boost their self-confidence, enhance their computer knowledge, and improve themselves. In addition, they are thankful that RMMC institution provided them with training and seminars that they used to teach amidst the COVID-19 pandemic online.

In Cyprus, Souleles et al. (2020) held that considering disciplinary distinctions and that e-learning is a subtraction to current teaching and learning approaches. Although it is a vital step, offering hastily organized seminars to fill in instructors' skill deficits cannot replace the requirement for ongoing training in both the pedagogical and technological fields.

Learn From Colleagues. It is significant to maintain good relationships with co-workers through listening and learning. Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, each of them listens to the ideas of others, asks how to navigate computer parts and functions, and always be willing to learn. Fortunately for them, their co-teachers were willing to offer help and shared their knowledge about the use of technology.

Lapada et al. (2020) and Pentang (2021) remarked that regardless of the conditions, instructors must employ accessible and suitable methodology to present their teachings successfully. Despite the problems provided by the COVID-19 epidemic, teachers continue to help by creating modules that serve as learning aids for pupils.

Insights of the Participants Amidst the Pandemic

As to the insights of the Criminology Faculty, six themes emerged, Accepting challenges, Being grateful, Developing oneself, Adapting different teaching styles, Motivating students, and Keeping the willingness to learn.

Table 3. Insights of the Criminology Faculty during the COVID-19 pandemic

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
<p>Appreciate that hardships lead to better changes Accept the positive and negative effect brought by pandemic in educational system Be open to new changes Take care of physical and mental health while dealing with the life's changes Realized that nothing is constant in this world except change Abide with the changes brought by COVID-19 pandemic Adapt with the changes and be flexible</p>	Accept Changes
<p>Be thankful with the work Move forward with a grateful heart despite circumstances Be grateful for the good health Thankful for all the blessings amidst pandemic Glorify the Lord for being safe</p>	Be Grateful
<p>Upgrade oneself Develop skills in writing, reading, and using online platforms Improve hobbies Be open for self-enhancement Watch YouTube tutorial on self-development during pandemic Engage in new activities Prioritize self-development Practice arranging specific works for a day Make oneself better by joining training about teaching related activities</p>	Develop Oneself
<p>Apply strategies on teaching online Join training and seminars related to improving different teaching strategies Abreast with the new teaching strategy Study and learn more about the use of computer Practice the use of Google Meet, Zoom, and other online teaching platforms Expose students with great teaching materials Go with the trend and improve quality of teaching Discover and explore the various types of teaching techniques</p>	Adapt Different Teaching Styles
<p>Make time for students Inspire students to do better Give quality time for students Never discourage the learners Encourage learners and make sure they learn a lot Be open to students and allow them to share their experiences</p>	Motivate Students
<p>Help each other to excel Offer help when needed Provide assistance for those who have lack of knowledge about computer Encourage colleagues to face the challenges in life with persistence Ask for help whenever necessary Embrace the challenges and face them together</p>	Keep the Willingness to Learn

Accept Changes. Participants shared their insights from what they have experienced through the challenges and the coping mechanisms they have made. According to them, appreciate hardships as it leads to better changes, accept both negative

and positive effects of COVID-19, be open to new changes, and take care of physical and mental health since it is the only source of continuation, instill in mind that there is no constant except changes, and adapt to the changes and be flexible.

There are adaptable choices for finishing course requirements during the academic year for students who cannot participate in online learning (De La Salle University, 2020). To allow "all students to learn at their speed," ADMU has halted synchronous online classes while maintaining asynchronous online learning Villarín (2020). Like DLSU, UST has chosen to keep using synchronous and asynchronous online courses and variable grading of student outputs and evaluations.

Be Grateful. The participants shared that after they experienced those challenges, they encountered still, people should be grateful despite what happened. Be grateful for having good health, thankful for all the blessings amidst the pandemic, glory to the *Lord* for being safe, and move forward with a grateful heart despite circumstances.

Despite a year of debates over masks and the existence of the pandemic, society is more interconnected than ever (Bersin, 2020). Zoom and Microsoft Teams have made it easier for individuals to communicate with one another despite many people being estranged from their families. Several calls happen throughout the day, and have never met face-to-face before. People spend a lot more time on the phone, watching videos, or browsing the internet website than in the past when commuting, traveling, or using public transportation. Furthermore, stronger ties result from this.

Develop Oneself. One of the insights that participants can share is what they see amidst the COVID-19 pandemic as individuals they have developed themselves. They have developed their skills in writing, reading, and using online platforms by engaging themselves in new activities, watching YouTube video tutorials, and improving themselves through training in teaching-related activities.

According to Huang et al. (2020), flexible learning is an educational method that incorporates a variety of student-centered teaching and learning approaches, resources, and administrative processes to meet the demands of a varied student population. On the other hand, Bridgland & Blanchard (2013; Winnie (1994), various governments worldwide encouraged flexible learning during the COVID-19 epidemic to reduce the impacts of academic disruption. The "Disrupted Classes, Undisrupted Learning" project was launched in China and intended to provide flexible online learning to over 270 million nationwide students from the comfort of their homes. According to Oliver (2001), in a similar vein, the Australian government developed the Flexible Learning Initiative. Project on Toolboxes The goal was to promote the use of flexible learning modes by making a collection of learning resources for web-based delivery available in a way that allowed for customization and reuse of existing infrastructure in the country's vocational education and training system.

Adapt Different Teaching Styles. According to the participants, to be able to remove negativity in the changes brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, they need to abreast themselves with new teaching strategies such as studying more to learn about computers, going with the trend to improve the quality of teaching, and apply strategies on teaching online from joining different training and seminars related to improving various teaching strategies.

As with any profession, some instructors are better than others. According to Barton (2019), some teachers have a calling, while others do it for vacation and pay. Maintaining instructors' motivation through professional development is crucial if they have the drive to master new teaching techniques and make their lesson plans engaging. The relevance of having the ability to adapt to a changing world is crucial in the educational environment. Which teaching approach will provide the best results, practically speaking, between a teacher who produces colorful presentations and games and one who still uses the traditional blackboard? It all boils down to the resources instructors can access and their knowledge of the best tools and tactics. If something is not helping with learning, we must try something else.

Motivate Students. The COVID-19 pandemic affected teachers and even students, who are far less aware of everything happening. Some are thinking of stopping their studies and finding a job. One of the reasons is that not everybody can afford gadgets and an internet connection. According to participants, as a teacher, ensure that there is a time for students, inspire them to do better, never discourage them, be open to students, and allow them to share their experiences.

Faculty members around the nation took on the difficult work of multitasking in the spring of 2020, including learning new technology, advising, holding online office hours, participating in formal meetings, replying to students who would request Zoom sessions outside of office hours, and much more (Nagpal, 2020). Everyone joined together for the benefit of the pupils as their overarching goal. It is essential to consider the long-term while making decisions as we go forward. Teachers must walk a fine line to keep kids engaged while maintaining their morale. Regardless of the study format chosen—online, blended, hybrid, or any variations—student motivation will be a big challenge.

Keep The Willingness to Learn. The last insight that participants can share is being willing to learn and offer help to others. Encouraging colleagues to face challenges with persistence, ask for assistance whenever necessary, embrace the challenges, face them together, and provide assistance to those who lack computer knowledge.

To rebuild better educational systems, countries must implement the teaching strategies that have proven successful during the remote learning phase and incorporate them into the standard education system. Investing in teachers' capacity-building and skill development is essential if they want to make the most of online and blended learning. It is equally crucial to free up teachers' time from administrative duties (like Brazil, Peru, and Uruguay did), concentrate on what is pedagogically sound, and give instructors socio-emotional support. As a result of the pandemic and prolonged school closures, teachers' roles have altered, and most were unprepared for this transformation. Maintaining health and avoiding burnout in teachers requires a detailed approach to socio-emotional monitoring and psychosocial assistance (Barron et al., 2021)

5. CONCLUSION

The experiences, challenges and coping mechanisms, and insights of the participants were from the result of this study. The results showed that all participants experienced hardships while teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The difficulties in signal processing contributed to the conclusions of this study based on the preceding part of this study. Sometimes classes were interrupted due to poor internet connection, and not all participants were technology-wise are the challenges that few of the participants felt and thought of quitting their job. Furthermore, experiences that some of them were gaining headaches, triggered eyes, and sleepless nights caused by prolonged use of computers, too much use of gadgets, and spending too much time online classes. Aside from health issues and internet connection problems, not all teachers were technology-wise. Many people found it difficult to create PowerPoint, Excel, or Microsoft Word since they needed to gain experience with various web platforms.

From the challenges above, fortunately, they found some coping mechanisms that help them to stay in line. According to them, they always trust the *Lord*, be optimistic so hard things might look easy, attend training and seminars in addition to already knowing that they have, and lastly, by listening to colleagues that already solved the current problem. Furthermore, there are still beneficial outcomes beyond those events that stress or harden teachers' lives.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abbas, K. A. (2021). *Factors influencing students reading comprehension difficulties amidst the use of modular distance learning approach in mindanao state university sulu – senior high school*. Open Access Indonesia Journal of Social Sciences, 4(2), 471–493. <https://doi.org/10.37275/oaijss.v4i2.78>
- [2] Abel, J. A., & Corcuera, L. (2021). *The webinar experiences of higher education instructors in the time of emergency remote education*. Uluslararası Eğitim Araştırmacıları Dergisi. <https://doi.org/10.52134/ueader.983093>
- [3] Adams, V. M., Game, E. T., & Bode, M. (2014). *Synthesis and review: delivering on conservation promises: the challenges of managing and measuring conservation outcomes*. Environmental Research Letters, 9(8), 085002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/9/8/085002>
- [4] Ainsworth, S., & Oldfield, J. (2019). *Quantifying teacher resilience: context matters*. Teaching and Teacher Education, 82, 117–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.03.012>
- [5] Agayon, A. J. D., Agayon, A. J. D., & Pentang, J. T. (2022). *Teachers in the new normal: challenges and coping mechanisms in secondary schools*. Journal of Humanities and Education Development, 4(1), 67–75. <https://doi.org/10.22161/jhed.4.1.8>
- [6] Ahmadi, R. M. (2018). *The use of technology in english language learning: a literature review*. International Journal of Research in English Education, 3(2), 115-125. <https://doi.org/10.29252/ijree.3.2.115>
- [7] Alderman, M. K. (2018). *Motivation for achievement: possibilities for teaching and learning*. <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA6810387X>
- [8] Allen, R.; Jerrim, J. and Sims, S. 2020. *How did the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic affect teacher wellbeing?* (CEPEO Working Paper No. 20-15). Centre for Education Policy and Equalising Opportunities, UCL, <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:ucl:cepeow:20-15>

- [9] Alshahrani, I. (2019). *Orienting faculty and students with online teaching webinar experiences in saudi arabia*. Annals of Medical and Health Sciences Research, 9(1). <https://www.amhsr.org/articles/orienting-faculty-and-students-with-online-teaching-webinar-experiences-in-saudi-arabia.pdf>
- [10] Alvarina, C., Aninipot, A., Doma, J., Hilig, C., Dollesin, A., Desuig, S. & Dimaano, A. (2022). *The impact assessment of work-from-home scheme among senior high schoolteachers in sorsogon national high school*. <https://www.scribd.com/document/569656773/Chapter-2-3I-s#>
- [11] Ayebi-Arthur, K. (2017). *E-learning, resilience and change in higher education: helping a university cope after a natural disaster*. E-learning and Digital Media, 14(5), 259–274. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2042753017751712>
- [12] Al-Fudail, M., & Mellar, H. (2008). *Investigating teacher stress when using technology*. Computers & Education, 51(3), 1103–1110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2007.11.004>
- [13] Bailey, J. N. (2008). *First steps in qualitative data analysis: transcribing*. Family Practice, 25(2), 127–131. <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmn003>
- [14] Barry, D. & Kanematsu, H. (2020). *Teaching during the covid-19 pandemic*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED606017.pdf>
- [15] Baguri, E. M., Roslan, S., Hassan, S. A., Krauss, S. E., & Zaremohzzabieh, Z. (2022). *How do self-esteem, dispositional hope, crisis self-efficacy, mattering, and gender differences affect teacher resilience during covid-19 school closures?* International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 19(7), 4150. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19074150>
- [16] Bao, W. (2020). *Covid-19 and online teaching in higher education: a case study of peking university*. Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies, 2, 113-115. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.191>
- [17] Bryman, A. (2012). *Social research methods*. Oxford University Press.
- [18] Barron, M., Cobo, C., Munoz-Najar, A., & Ciarrusta, I. S. (2021). *The changing role of teachers and technologies amidst the covid 19 pandemic: key findings from a cross-country study*. World Bank Blogs. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/education/changing-role-teachers-and-technologies-amidst-covid-19-pandemic-key-findings-cross>
- [19] Baker, J. S. (2021). *Poetry and possible selves: crisis theory with/in teacher education programs*. Teaching and Teacher Education, 105, 103393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103393>
- [20] Bao, W. (2020). *Covid-19 and online teaching in higher education: a case study of peking university*. Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies, 2, 113-115. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.191>
- [21] Bozkurt, A., & Sharma, R. C. (2020). *Emergency remote teaching in a time of global crisis due to coronavirus pandemic*. Asian Journal of Distance Education, 15(1), i-vi. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3778083>
- [22] Bersin, J. (2020). *Despite the pandemic, we have a lot to be thankful for*. Josh Bersin. <https://joshbersin.com/2020/11/despite-the-pandemic-we-have-a-lot-to-be-thankful-for/>
- [23] Bleck, V., & Lipowsky, F. (2022). *Teachers' emotional exhaustion before and during the covid-19 pandemic: neither emotional exertion nor vacation feeling*. Frontiers in Psychology, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.887494>
- [24] Cos, F. L., Duero, M., & Paguia, M. R. S. (2021). *The viability of deped textbooks as the primary material for the modular distance learning modality of carrascal national high school*. Journal of Food and Nutrition Research, 1(2), 69–75. <https://doi.org/10.12691/jitl-1-2-2>
- [25] Crawford, J., Jurgen, R., Henderson, K. & Malkawi, B. (2020). *Covid-19: 20 countries' higher education intra-period digital pedagogy responses*. Journal of Applied Learning and Teaching, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2020.3.1.7>
- [26] Caratiquit, K., & Caratiquit, L. J. (2022). *Uncovering teacher's situation amidst the pandemic: teacher's coping mechanisms, initiatives, constraints, and challenges encountered*. International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research, 288–298. <https://doi.org/10.24289/ijsser.1103698>
- [27] Chan, E. (2019). *Blended learning dilemma: teacher education in the confucian heritage culture*. Australian Journal of Teacher Education, 36–51. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2018v44n1.3>

- [28] Castroverde, F., & Acala, M. (2021). Modular distance learning modality: challenges of teachers in teaching amid the covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 10(8). <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2021.602>
- [29] Cheng, C.M. & Bakar, M.B.A. (2017). The impact of using modules in the teaching and learning of english in malaysian polytechnics: an analysis of the views and perceptions of english language teaching. *Jabatan Pengajian Am*. <https://www.pdfFiller.com/414042298--the-impact-of-using-modules-in-the-teaching-and-learning-of-english-in-malaysian-polytechnics-an-analysis-of-the-views-and-perceptions-of-english-language-lecturers->
- [30] Crossman, A. (2020). An overview of qualitative research methods. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/qualitative-research-methods-3026555>
- [31] Creswell, J.W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: choosing among the five approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc. (pp. 77-83)
- [32] Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE.
- [33] Daniel, J. (2020). *Education and the covid-19 pandemic*. *Prospects*, 49(1–2), 91–96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-020-09464-3>
- [34] De Villa, J. A., & Manalo, F. K. B. (2020). Secondary teachers' preparation, challenges and coping mechanism in the pre-implementation of distance learning in the new normal. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 144–154. <https://doi.org/10.54476/iimrj345>
- [35] Dangle, Y.R.P. & Sumaoang, J.D. (2020). The implementation of modular distance learning in the Philippine secondary public schools. <https://doi.org/10.33422/3rd.icate.2020.11.132>
- [36] Dilna, A., Guiamalon, T., & Dilna, S. (2022). Teachers' adaptation and practices amidst pandemic. <http://ijasos.ocerintjournals.org/tr/download/article-file/2532301>
- [37] DepEd. (2020). DepEd prepares self-learning modules for education's new normal. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/07/02/deped-prepares-self-learning-modules-for-educations-new-normal/>
- [38] De La Salle University (2020a). *Coping with challenges and learning during the enhanced community quarantine period*. Available online at: <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/2nd-term-faqs/>
- [39] Dziuban, C. D., Graham, C. R., Moskal, P., Norberg, A., & Sicilia, N. (2018). Blended learning: the new normal and emerging technologies. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-017-0087-5>
- [40] Drayton, B., Falk, J.K., Stroud, R., Hobbs, K., & Hammerman, M.J. (2010). After installation: ubiquitous computing and high school science in three experienced, high-technology schools. *Journal of Technology, Learning, and Assessment*, 9(3).
- [41] Edara, I. R., Del Castillo, F., Ching, G. S., & Del Castillo, C. D. (2021). Religiosity and contentment among teachers in the philippines during covid-19 pandemic: mediating effects of resilience, optimism, and well-being. *Religions*, 12(10), 879. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12100879>
- [42] ECW. (2020). Education cannot wait. From COVID-19 and Education in Emergencies: <https://www.educationcannotwait.org/covid-19/>
- [43] Fang, Y., Liu, P., & Gao, Q. (2021). *Assessment of knowledge, attitude, and practice toward covid-19 in china: an online cross-sectional survey*. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 104(4), 1461–1471. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.20-0452>
- [44] Giovannella, C., Passarelli, M., & Persico, D. (2020). The effects of the covid-19 pandemic on Italian learning ecosystems: the school teachers' perspective at the steady state. *Interaction Design and Architecture(S)*, 45, 264–286. <https://doi.org/10.55612/s-5002-045-012>

- [45] Geldsetzer, P. (2020). Use of rapid online surveys to assess people's perceptions during infectious disease outbreaks: a cross-sectional survey on covid-19. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(4), e18790. <https://doi.org/10.2196/18790>
- [46] Ghanbari, N., & Nowroozi, S. (2022). Iranian efl teachers' challenges and coping strategies during covid-19 pandemic: a case study. *The Qualitative Report*. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2022.5066>
- [47] Gazulla, E. D., Bauters, M., Hietala, I., Leinonen, T., & Kapros, E. (2019). Co-creation and co-design in technology-enhanced learning: innovating science learning outside the classroom. *Interaction Design and Architecture(S)*, 42, 202–226. <https://doi.org/10.55612/s-5002-042-010>
- [48] Gumarang, B. K. (2021). Private school teachers' voice in the philippines amidst covid-19 pandemic: a descriptive phenomenological study. Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5726586>
- [49] Graneheim U. H., Lundman B. (2004). *Qualitative content analysis in nursing research: concepts, procedures and measures to achieve trustworthiness*. *Nurse Education Today*, 24, 105-112.
- [50] Gubalani, R. (2021). Soccsksargen colleges, universities adjusted to flexible learning. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1146503>
- [51] George, T. (2022). Types of interviews in research. Guide and examples. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/interviews-research/>
- [52] Henderson, D., Woodcock, H. V., Mehta, J. B., Khan, N., Shivji, V., Richardson, C. L., Aya, H., Ziser, S., Pollara, G., & Burns, A. (2020). Keep calm and carry on learning: using microsoft teams to deliver a medical education programme during the covid-19 pandemic. *Future Healthcare Journal*, 7(3), e67–e70. <https://doi.org/10.7861/fhj.2020-0071>
- [53] Hagan, J., Quansah, F., Ankomah, F., Agormedah, E. K., Srem-Sai, M., Frimpong, J. B., & Schack, T. (2022). Linking covid-19-related awareness and anxiety as determinants of coping strategies' utilization among senior high school teachers in cape coast metropolis, ghana. *Social Sciences*, 11(3), 137. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11030137>
- [54] Hart, C. (2020). Coaching for teacher resilience during covid-19. Research Triangle institute international. <https://www.rti.org/insights/coaching-teacher-resilience-during-covid-19-burnout-and-trauma>
- [55] Hidalgo-Andrade, P., Hermosa-Bosano, C., & Paz, C. (2021). Teachers' mental health and self-reported coping strategies during the covid-19 pandemic in ecuador: a mixed-methods study. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, Volume 14, 933–944. <https://doi.org/10.2147/prbm.s314844>
- [56] Huang, Y. & Zhao, N. (2020b). Generalized anxiety disorder, depressive symptoms and sleep quality during covid-19 outbreak in china: a web-based cross-sectional survey. *Psychiatry Research-neuroimaging*, 288, 112954. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112954>
- [57] Hagan, J., Quansah, F., Ankomah, F., Agormedah, E. K., Srem-Sai, M., Frimpong, J. B., & Schack, T. (2022). Linking covid-19-related awareness and anxiety as determinants of coping strategies' utilization among senior high school teachers in cape coast metropolis, ghana. *Social Sciences*, 11(3), 137. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11030137>
- [58] Hanson, J. (2009). *Displaced but not replaced: the impact of e-learning on academic identities in higher education*. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 14(5), 553–564. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562510903186774>
- [59] Heinze, A. and C. Procter (2004). Reflections on the use of blended learning. education in a changing environment. Conference proceedings, University of Salford, Salford, Education Development Unit.
- [60] Johnson, N. L., Veletsianos, G., & Seaman, J. C. (2020). *U.s. Faculty and administrators' experiences and approaches in the early weeks of the covid-19 pandemic*. *Online Learning*, 24(2). <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v24i2.2285>
- [61] Jones, A., & Kessler, M. A. (2020). *Teachers' emotion and identity work during a pandemic*. *Frontiers in Education*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2020.583775>

- [62] Kamal, T., & Illiyan, A. (2021). School teachers' perception and challenges towards online teaching during covid-19 pandemic in india: an econometric analysis. *Asian Association of Open Universities Journal*, 16(3), 311–325. <https://doi.org/10.1108/aaouj-10-2021-0122>
- [63] Kim, L. E., & Asbury, K. (2020). Like a rug had been pulled from under you': the impact of covid-19 on teachers in england during the first six weeks of the uk lockdown. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 90(4), 1062–1083. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12381>
- [64] Kim, J. J., Munroe, M., Feng, Z. C., Morris, S., Al-Refae, M., Antonacci, R., & Ferrari, M. D. (2021). Personal growth and well-being in the time of covid: an exploratory mixed-methods analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.648060>
- [65] Ketchell, M. (2018). The hidden threat of teacher stress. *The conversation*. <https://theconversation.com/the-hidden-threat-of-teacher-stress-92676>
- [66] Klusmann, U., Aldrup, K., Roloff-Bruchmann, J., Ertanir, B., Wartenberg, G., Hansen, J., & Hanewinkel, R. (2022). Teachers' emotional exhaustion during the covid-19 pandemic: levels, changes, and relations to pandemic-specific demands. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 121, 103908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2022.103908>
- [67] Klapproth, F., Federkeil, L., Heinschke, F., & Jungmann, T. (2020). Teachers experiences of stress and their coping strategies during covid - 19 induced distance teaching. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 4(4), 444–452. <https://doi.org/10.33902/jpr.2020062805>
- [68] Kawinkoonlasate, P. (2020). Online language learning for thai efl learners: an analysis of effective alternative learning methods in response to the covid-19 outbreak. *English Language Teaching*, 13(12), 15. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v13n12p15>
- [69] Kelly S. (2010). Qualitative interviewing techniques and styles. In: Bourgeault I, Dingwall R, de Vries R. (eds) *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Methods in Health Research*, Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications
- [70] Kent (2021). *Germany kent quotes*. <https://bookroo.com/quotes/germany-kent>
- [71] Lau, H., Khosrawipour, V., Kocbach, P., Mikolajczyk, A., Schubert, J., Bania, J., & Khosrawipour, T. (2020). The positive impact of lockdown in wuhan on containing the covid-19 outbreak in china. *Journal of Travel Medicine*, 27(3). <https://doi.org/10.1093/jtm/taaa037>
- [72] Lapada, A.A., Miguel, F.F., Robledo, D.A.R. & Alam, Z. (2020) Teachers' covid-19 awareness, distance learning education experiences and perceptions towards institutional readiness and challenges. *Lapada | International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*. <https://www.ijlter.org/index.php/ijlter/article/view/2231>
- [73] Ley, T., Tammets, K., Sarmiento-Márquez, E. M., Leoste, J., Hallik, M., & Poom-Valickis, K. (2021). Adopting technology in schools: modelling, measuring and supporting knowledge appropriation. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 45(4), 548–571. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2021.1937113>
- [74] Lincoln, Y., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- [75] Lagat, K. T. (2021). Factors affecting teachers' resiliency amidst the covid-19 pandemic. *Recoletos Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(1), 133–145. <https://doi.org/10.32871/rmrj2109.01.12>
- [76] Milasi, S., Gonzalez-Vasquez, I. & Fernandez-Macias, E. (2020). Telework in the eu before and after the covid-19: where we were, where we head to. https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-06/jrc120945_policy_brief_-_covid_and_telework_final.pdf
- [77] Macaraeg, C. A., Barcelo, J. R., Reyes, D. N. G., Mercurio, M. E., Bernardo, J. A., & Santos, M. (2021). Modular distance learning expenses of senior high school teachers amidst the pandemic. *International Journal of English, Literature and Social Science*, 6(3), 259–263. <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijels.63.35>
- [78] Malipot, M. (2020). Deped calibrating learning delivery processes. <https://mb.com.ph/2020/10/30/depd-calibrating-learning-delivery-processes/>

- [79] Ma, K., Chutiyami, M., Zhang, Y., & Nicoll, S. (2021). Online teaching self-efficacy during covid-19: changes, its associated factors and moderators. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 6675–6697. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10486-3>
- [80] Mishra, L., Gupta, T., & Shree, A. (2020). Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 1, 100012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2020.100012>
- [81] Meidl, M. (2014) How to rely on your faith during hard times. <https://www.osfhealthcare.org/blog/how-to-rely-on-your-faith-during-hard-times/>
- [82] McNaughton, S., & Billot, J. (2016). Negotiating academic teacher identity shifts during higher education contextual change. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 21(6), 644–658. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2016.1163669>
- [83] Moustakas, C. (1994). *Phenomenological research methods*. Sage.
- [84] Nascimbeni, F., & Burgos, D. (2016). In search for the open educator: proposal of a definition and a framework to increase openness adoption among university educators. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 17(6), 1–10. <http://www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/view/2736/3974>
- [85] Nyambongi, P.M. (2014). Causes of stress among teachers in public secondary schools: a case of public secondary schools in starehe district.
- [86] Nagpal, S. (2020). Raising student motivation during pandemic. <https://www.facultyfocus.com/articles/effective-teaching-strategies/raising-student-motivation-during-the-pandemic/>
- [87] Online Purdue. (2020). *How has technology changed education?* <https://online.purdue.edu/blog/education/how-has-technology-changed-education>
- [88] Osguthorpe, R. T. & Graham, C. R. (2003). *Blended learning environments: definitions and directions*. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 4(3), 227–233.
- [89] Putra, P., Liriwati, F. Y., Tahrim, T., Syafrudin, S., & Aslan, A. (2020). The students learning from home experiences during covid-19 school closures policy in indonesia. *Jurnal Iqra' : Kajian Ilmu Pendidikan*, 5(2), 30–42. <https://doi.org/10.25217/ji.v5i2.1019>
- [90] Pöysä, S., Pakarinen, E., & Lerkkanen, M. (2021). Patterns of teachers' occupational well-being during the covid-19 pandemic: relations to experiences of exhaustion, recovery, and interactional styles of teaching. *Frontiers in Education*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.699785>
- [91] Pentang, J. (2021). The concept of curriculum and its foundation. *The Educator's Link*, 1(6), 9. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355953574_The_Concept_of_Curriculum_Foundation
- [92] Pachiyappan, T., Kumar, K. V., Mark, P., Venugopal, R., Jilumudi, D., & Palanisamy, B. N. (2021b). A study on the histological and biochemical effects of long-term exposure of 4g lte radiation emitted by mobile phone on the liver of wistar rats. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Health Care*, 13(2), 139–145. <https://doi.org/10.18311/ajprhc/2021/26836>
- [93] Polit D. F. & Beck C. T. (2012). *Nursing research: principles and methods*. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- [94] Quansah, F., Frimpong, J. B., Sambah, F., Oduro, P., Anin, S. K., Srem-Sai, M., Hagan, J., & Schack, T. (2022). Covid-19 pandemic and teachers' classroom safety perception, anxiety and coping strategies during instructional delivery. *Healthcare*, 10(5), 920. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10050920>
- [95] Quezada, R. L., Talbot, C., & Quezada-Parker, K. B. (2020). From bricks and mortar to remote teaching: a teacher education program's response to covid-19. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 46(4), 472–483. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2020.1801330>
- [96] Quintos, C., Caballes, D. G., Gapad, E., & Valdez, M. R. (2021). Perceptions of teachers on the different strains of online modality of learning. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349176836_Perceptions_of_Teachers_on_the_Different_Strains_of_Online_Modality_of_Learning

- [97] Rao, P.S. (2019). *The influence of webinars in developing teaching skills of the english language teachers: a comprehensive study in elt* https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338411712_THE_INFLUENCE_OF_WEBINARS_IN_DEVELOPING_TEACHING_SKILLS_OF_THE_ENGLISH_LANGUAGE_TEACHERS_A_COMPREHENSIVE_STUDY_IN_ELT
- [98] Revathi, S., Nair, S. & Achuthan, A. (2020). *Influence of technological gadgets on health and lifestyle of medico*. National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy Pharmacology. <https://doi.org/10.5455/njppp.2020.10.12377201908012020>
- [99] Roy, H., Ray, K., Saha, S., & Ghosai, A. K. (2020). *A study on students' perceptions for online zoom-app based flipped class sessions on anatomy organised during the lockdown period of covid-19 epoch*. Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research. <https://doi.org/10.7860/jcdr/2020/44869.13797>
- [100] Ratanasiripong, P., China, T., Ratanasiripong, N. T., & Toyama, S. (2020). *Resiliency and mental health of school teachers in okinawa*. Journal of Health Research, 35(6), 470–481. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jhr-11-2019-0248>
- [101] Rogers, P. L. (2001). *Traditions to transformations: the forced evolution of higher education*. Educational Technology Review, 9(1).
- [102] Raducu, C., & Stănculescu, E. (2021). *Adaptability to online teaching during covid-19 pandemic: a multiple mediation analysis based on kolb's theory*. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 18(15), 8032. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18158032>
- [103] Robosa, J., Perante, L., Paras, N.E. & Alvez, T. (2021). *The experiences and challenges faced of the public school teachers amidst the covid-19 pandemic: a phenomenological study in the philippines*. DOI:10.6084/m9.figshare.14028833.v1
- [104] Sahu, P. K. (2020). *Closure of universities due to coronavirus disease 2019 (covid-19): impact on education and mental health of students and academic staff*. Cureus. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.7541>
- [105] Swartz, B., Gachago, D., & Belford, C. (2018). *To care or not to care - reflections on the ethics of blended learning in times of disruption*. South African Journal of Higher Education, 32(6). <https://doi.org/10.20853/32-6-2659>
- [106] Sawchuck, S. & Samuels, C. (2020). *Where are they? students go missing in shift to remote classes*. [://www.edweek.org/leadership/where-are-they-students-go-missing-in-shift-to-remote-classes/2020/04](http://www.edweek.org/leadership/where-are-they-students-go-missing-in-shift-to-remote-classes/2020/04)
- [107] Strauss, V. (2020). *A veteran teacher has a mini covid-19 educator meltdown – and realizes that less is more with online learning*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/education/2020/04/08/veteran-teacher-has-mini-covid-19-educator-meltdown-realizes-that-less-is-more-with-online-learning/>
- [108] Schleicher, A. (2020). *The impact of covid-19 on education: insight from education at a glance 2020*. <https://www.oecd.org/education/the-impact-of-covid-19-on-education-insights-education-at-a-glance-2020.pdf>
- [109] Schaffhauser, D. (2020). *Educators feeling stressed, anxious overwhelmed and capable*. <https://thejournal.com/articles/2020/06/02/survey-teachers-feeling-stressed-anxious-overwhelmed-and-capable.aspx>
- [110] Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2018). *Job demands and job resources as predictors of teacher motivation and well-being*. Social Psychology of Education, 21(5), 1251–1275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-018-9464-8>
- [111] Soria, W. V. N., & Naparan, G. B. (2022). *Elementary teachers' challenges and coping strategies in the radio-based instruction and modular distance learning. (2022)*. International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v9i2p240>
- [112] Sandelowski, M. (1986). *The problem of rigor in qualitative research*. Advances in Nursing Science, 8(3), 27–37. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00012272-198604000-00005>
- [113] Smit, B., & Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2018). *Observations in qualitative inquiry: when what you see is not what you see*. International Journal of Qualitative Methods, 17(1), 160940691881676. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406918816766>
- [114] Schrum, L. & Levin, B.B. (2009). *Leading 21st century schools: harnessing technology for engagement and achievement*. Corwin: Thousand Oaks, CA.

- [115] Setiawan, A. R. (2020). Scientific literacy worksheets for distance learning in the topic of coronavirus 2019 (covid-19). Reading Academic Articles.
- [116] Salmon, G. (2002). E-tivities: the key to active online learning. London: Kogan Page Limited.
- [117] Souleles, N., Laghos, A., & Savva, S. (2020). From face-to-face to online: assessing the effectiveness of the rapid transition of higher education due to the coronavirus outbreak. In ICERI proceedings. International Academy of Technology, Education and Development. <https://doi.org/10.21125/iceri.2020.0274>
- [118] The Lancet, N. (2020). *India under covid-19 lockdown*. The Lancet, 395(10233), 1315. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30938-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30938-7)
- [119] Teo, C. L., Chee, M. L., Koh, K. S., Tseng, R. M. W. W., Majithia, S., Thakur, S., Gunasekeran, D. V., Nusinovici, S., Sabanayagam, C., Wong, T. Y., Tham, Y. C., & Cheng, C. (2021). *Covid-19 awareness, knowledge and perception towards digital health in an urban multi-ethnic asian population*. Scientific Reports, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-90098-6>
- [120] Tosun, N., Mihci, C., & Bayzan, Ş. (2021). *Challenges encountered by in-service k12 teachers at the beginning of the covid-19 pandemic period: the case of turkey*. Participatory Educational Research, 8(4), 359–384. <https://doi.org/10.17275/per.21.95.8.4>
- [121] UNESCOa. (2020). May 16. *Covid-19 educational disruption and response*. <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>
- [122] Van Lancker, W., & Parolin, Z. (2020). *Covid-19, school closures, and child poverty: a social crisis in the making*. The Lancet. Public Health, 5(5), e243–e244. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-2667\(20\)30084-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2468-2667(20)30084-0)
- [123] Villarín, J. R. T. (2020). *Enhanced community quarantine*. Quezon City, PH: Ateneo de Manila University.
- [124] Vulpe, L., & Pribac, S. (2021). *Teachers' adaptability to online education during covid-19*. Revista De Ştiinţe Ale Educaţiei, 44(2), 63–78. <https://doi.org/10.35923/jes.2021.2.05>
- [125] Weinert, S., Thronicke, A., Hinse, M., Schad, F., & Matthes, H. (2021). *School teachers' self-reported fear and risk perception during the covid-19 pandemic—a nationwide survey in germany*. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18179218>
- [126] Wyman, O. (2020). *Education in the new normal: education leadership response to covid19*. http://oliverwyman.com/content/dam/oliverwyman/v2/publications/2020/jun/Education_In_The_New_Normal.pdf
- [127] Xu, C., Li, Y., Chen, P., Pan, M., & Bu, X. (2020). *A survey on the attitudes of chinese medical students towards current pathology education*. BMC Medical Education, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-020-02167-5>
- [128] Yikici, B., Altınay, F., Altınay, Z., Sharma, R., & Dagi, G. (2022). *Adoption of online education and pedagogy as new codes of life for new future in rural regions*. Sustainability, 14(9), 5528. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095528>